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The Role of Preventive Conservation in Designing King Tutankhamun Galleries in the Grand Egyptian Museum

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Abstract

It was decided to display the whole collection of King Tutankhamun in the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM). The collection comprises approx. 5640 objects different in material and state of conservation. The conservation centre in the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM-CC) bears the responsibility of conserving GEM collection, and contributing to the exhibition production processes to ensure the optimal preservation for the collection on display. In this paper, a survey of the collection's materials and condition was undertaken to evaluate the risks and corresponding deterioration occurred in the former location which should be mitigated in the new one. It also reports on the parameters which were fulfilled in the designs of King Tutankhamun galleries to guarantee implementing preventive conservation programmes in order to preserve the collection for future generations.

Keywords: Preservation; exhibition; Tutankhamun; preventive conservation; showcase; mount; Grand Egyptian Museum; environmental control

1. Introduction

The treasure of King Tutankhamun that was discovered in Luxor in 1922 by Howard Carter comprises a vast number of objects made of different materials; organic, inorganic and composite of the highest artistic and historical significance. Most of these artefacts were transported after discovery to the galleries and storerooms of the Egyptian Museum (EM) in Cairo. Unfortunately, the museum's poor infrastructure did not facilitate the implementation of preventive conservation programmes, and the displayed and stored objects faced c.80 years of degradation by different factors.

The Egyptian Government commenced the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM) project in 2002 to house about 100,000 artefacts including the whole collection of King Tutankhamun. GEM which is currently under construction on a 470-hectare site overlooking the Pyramids of Giza will become the largest museums of Egyptian antiquities in the world. About 7500 square metres of the museum's display area is dedicated to exhibit the collection of King Tutankhamun (Figure 1). In the second phase of the GEM project in 2010, GEM-CC was opened to protect the GEM collection by providing necessary conservation treatments and ensuring the implementation of preservation programmes in galleries and storerooms.

It is very well known that improperly designed and poorly fabricated exhibition spaces are significant sources of damage for museum collections (Raphael and Burke 2000). For that reason, preventive

conservation measures and practices were taken into account when designing and creating the GEM displays. As a starting point, conservation guidelines were developed to preserve the collection in galleries. Discussions and review with conservators, curators, engineers and exhibit designers were held to guarantee the implementation of preventive conservation programmes in the King Tutankhamun galleries. This study focuses merely on the preservation of Tutankhamun collection in galleries and does not include security or emergency responses (fire, earthquake, etc.).

Figure 1: Tutankhamun gallery (under construction) in the GEM with a total area of 7500m² and a gable wall with 19 m high ceiling. Photo: Hussein Kamal.

2. Survey of the King Tutankhamun collection

In order to understand the collection under study, identify the particular risks and accordingly prioritise the preventive conservation requirements in the galleries, it was necessary to embark on a survey of the

materials and conditions of the collection. The transportation of most of the collection to GEM-CC facilitated the investigation, analyses and accurate documentation of the current state of deterioration.

Generally, the collection comprises about 5640 artefacts, different in materials; organic (wood, textile, plant fibres, ivory, hair, mummies and human remains), inorganic (stone, glass, metal, pottery, faience and terra-cotta) and composite (made of various different materials and/or layers).

2.1 Inorganic artefacts

Artefacts made of inorganic materials, about 3321 objects, represent 59% of the whole collection. They are divided into two groups according to the composition. The first group comprises 2487 objects made of a sole inorganic material such as shabti tools which are made of copper. The second group comprises 834 objects made of different inorganic materials, such as the golden mask which is made of gold, glass and stones.

Although inorganic artefacts represent the highest percentage of the collection, most of them are individually very small and represent repetitive examples such as the 1831 shabti agricultural tools. In fact, this category exhibited the least deterioration under the storage conditions. This is because they are made of chemically stable materials such as gold, precious stones, rocks, etc. except for those made of relatively vulnerable materials such as metals and metal alloys which exhibited different corrosion patterns, probably due to previous conservation treatments, poor air quality and improper relative humidity (RH), such as the agricultural tools: hoes, yokes and baskets (Elmarazky et al. 2017).

2.2 Organic artefacts

Artefacts made of organic materials, about 1378 objects, represent 24% of the collection. They are considered more complicated than inorganic artefacts. They are also divided into two groups according to their composition. The first group comprises 941 objects made of a single organic material, such as measuring rods and meat boxes which are made exclusively of wood. The second group comprises 437 objects made of several organic materials, such as the marquetry jewellery box which is made of wood and ivory.

Organic materials are considered the most deteriorated objects among the collection (Figure 2), due to unsuitable display and storage conditions. The worst example may be the deterioration that occurred to one ceremonial fan due to light, ultraviolet radiation (Pedersoli, Antomarchi and Michalski 2016) and elevated temperature, and the deterioration of mummies which were stored until 2014 at the anatomy department in the Faculty of Medicine, Cairo University (Figure 3). Many other organic objects have already been found in poor condition during excavation, such as carbonised textiles; however unsuitable levels of light, RH, temperature, and insect attack contributed to further deterioration, particularly in folded items. Organic objects made exclusively of wood such as boomerangs, on the other hand, are more resistant under the same conditions. The woods used in this collection are of good quality, for example, ebony and mahogany.

2.3 Composite artefacts

Artefacts made of composite materials, about 941 objects, represent 17% of the collection. They are the most complicated objects, such as a gilded wooden figure of Anubis made of wood, gold, gesso and bronze. Composite materials are the most prone to deterioration because they have diverse materials and/or layers, whose response to environmental conditions, particularly temperature and RH, is quite different as is their deterioration. Shrines and beds which consist mainly of wood covered with different layers of

organic and inorganic matters, such as gold, gesso, pigments, and resin and sandals which consist of leather, gold and plant fibres are good examples (Figure 4). Risks were identified based on the former exhibition and storage locations for the collection, materials (Figure 5(a)) and condition due to five major agents of deterioration: improper environmental conditions, light, pests, poor air quality and physical forces. In most cases, the five agents of deterioration impacted on the whole collection, while in some cases, deterioration can be attributed to a single cause. For example, the effect of light is obvious on 30 displayed textile objects (tunics, loincloth, etc.) as fading and bleaching, while damage from insects is very clear on 313 stored textile objects as holes and losses. Additionally, fluctuating temperature and RH caused detachment of layers and buckling resulted from the dimensional changes in wood for gilded and decorated wooden objects, such as shrines, chariots and beds. Figure 5(b) illustrates the result of the survey of the collection condition demonstrating the number of damages observed according to the agent of deterioration.

Figure 2: (a) Folded tunic of King Tutankhamun in poor condition, stored in the EM. (b) During unfolding at GEM-CC. (c) and (d) Decoration patterns on tunic fragments. Photo: Hussein Kamal

Figure 3: Mummies showing severe deterioration on arrival at GEM-CC. Photo: Hussein Kamal.

Figure 4: (a) Folded tunic of King Tutankhamun in poor condition, stored in the EM. (b) During unfolding at GEM-CC. (c) and (d) Decoration patterns on tunic fragments. Photo: Hussein Kamal

Figure 5: (a) Distribution of material types in the collection of Tutankhamun. (b). Damage according to the agent of deterioration.

3. Environmental control in Tutankhamun Galleries in the GEM

The environmental standards for museum collection have been much debated in recent years (Bratasz2013), moving from the precautionary principle of minimising risk by selecting temperature and RH bands that are tight and constant to the principle of reducing energy consumption in museums (Staniforth2014) and ensuring sustainability (Bickersteth 2014).

In September 2014, delegates at both the IIC congress in Hong Kong and the ICOM-CC triennial meeting in Melbourne agreed on broader environmental parameters with acceptable fluctuations (Bickersteth2014). This was also agreed by AIC, AICCM and the Bizot group. Based on the materials and conditions of Tutankhamun collection and the facilities of the GEM building, it was decided to unite the two approaches to ensure optimal collection preservation, reduce energy consumption and guarantee sustainability.

3.1 Temperature and RH

Inappropriate temperature and RH levels cause direct and/or indirect irreversible damage. The collection of King Tutankhamun has long been subjected in the EM to unsuitable temperatures and RH levels and extreme daily and seasonal fluctuations, leading to corrosion, cracking, deformation, loosening of joints, fracture, delamination. Different environmental are required inside the gallery, particularly for some objects made of organic and composite materials.

The facilities of the GEM galleries comprise a heating, ventilation and air conditioning system (HVAC), providing 21–25°C up to 3 m height in the gallery. The temperature is stabilised with cooled air 18–19°C fed from floor ducts and inlets. The RH oscillates between 35% and 55% in the gallery space even with the influx of visitors. As the museum building envelope is well sealed, the temperature and RH are expected to fluctuate within acceptable ranges after turning the HVAC system off. However, unlikely or unacceptable fluctuations will be detected by the temperature and RH monitors in exhibition spaces and cases. In such case, further control by the HVAC system could be achieved.

Moreover, the collection will be displayed in 106 showcases built out of powder coated steel and two types of resistant safety glass (P4A and P6B) based on the security level. Each showcase will contain a technical compartment for passively buffering the interior RH, to ensure easy maintenance and reduced energy consumption. The airtightness of showcases will prolong the usefulness of the passive buffer (Shiner 2007) and guarantee minimal air changes per day. Twenty-eight showcases too large for passive absorbers will be equipped with an active humidity control system. The survey revealed that subsets of the collection require restricted bands of temperature and RH; including textiles, flower bouquets, wigs, hats, tools, raw materials and corn figures of Osiris. Such objects will be displayed in nine showcases equipped with active RH and temperature control system. Two oxygen-free microclimate showcases will display three objects; two mummies and one ceremonial fan, as they are in extremely poor condition. The fan, which should be displayed with other five fans according to the presentation theme 'Lifestyle', will be isolated in a small oxygen-free case inside the large case comprising the other five fans.

At the planning stage, it was presumed that operating the HVAC 24 hours per day would significantly increase energy consumption yet never be sufficient to provide the require environment for the whole varied collection. On the other hand, operating active humidity control systems in all cases would also greatly increase the energy consumption and would not guarantee sustainability because of the maintenance problems. Therefore, the environmental control strategy in Tutankhamun galleries involves operating the HVAC system only for visitors' comfort during museum opening hours, while employing

passive RH buffering in the airtight exhibit cases, except for some vulnerable objects, as summarised in Figure 6(a).

3.2 Light

Light causes irreversible damage (Smith 2010) to museum collections. All wavelengths of light cause significant damage to most objects (Lake 2011), governed by many factors including the sensitivity of objects, exposure duration (Muething, Waller and Graham 2005), type of lighting system, and the proximity and intensity of light. Light was one of the main agents of deterioration to the Tutankhamun collection which was exposed for about 80 years in the EM to direct daylight from windows glazed with ordinary glass and left open during the day, as well as artificial tungsten lighting in some closed galleries and inside showcases.

The lighting strategy of Tutankhamun galleries is based on an assessment of sensitivity to light while considering viewing conditions. There is a policy of reducing both light intensity and exposure time particularly for high-sensitivity materials and using highly efficient lighting equipment. Based on the collection survey, suitable lighting for each artefact was defined individually, according to sensitivity. Generally, the collection has three levels of sensitivity to light. Highly sensitive objects include mainly organic objects, mummies, textiles, leather, dyes, and papyrus. Moderately sensitive objects included wood, furniture, horn, bone and ivory. The least sensitive objects included most metal, faience, stones and glass.

The light intensity is reduced by providing a 'Blackbox' gallery in which 98% of daylight is removed and only 2% is allowed to transmit through screens covering the complete windows of the gable wall. Space between the screens is also covered. This small amount of daylight reaches less than 50 lux in the gallery, enough to provide natural way finding for the visitor's journey. At night, when no light enters the gallery, indirect wall illumination and ceiling lighting elements will be used, to illuminate the gallery with about 10–50 lux. Additionally, all showcases will have remotely controlled integral lighting.

It was necessary to reduce light exposure to prolong the lifetime of the artefacts. One approach is to substitute the artefacts in display, particularly textiles, for other similar items. Another approach is to install motion detectors in the showcases displaying extremely sensitive objects such as the mummies and to activate lighting only when a person is present in front of the case. Moreover, a building management system (BMS) will be utilised, to provide lighting setpoints for the ceiling lights, the indirect wall illumination, and the showcases. It will be used to control all the fixtures for emergency lighting and non-open periods. All fixtures are based on the latest LED technology with the highest efficiency and a colour rendering index > 90/95/97 to provide high visual comfort (Figure 6(b)).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Tutankhamun galleries. (a) The active climate control systems and (b) the showcase lighting system gallery, showing the indirect LED light source in the corner separated from the case interior using glass, with easy accessibility to the lighting compartment from outside the case, dimmers to control light, and cooling ribs to avoid heat build-up

3.3 Pests

The risk is infestation by insects and rodents, manifested as holes, tunnels, live captures, moulted skins, etc. The garden surrounding the EM along with the open exhibit areas (doors and sometimes windows) was the main cause, with poorly or improperly sealed showcases, and no pest monitoring or control procedure. The affected objects included folded textiles, wood, mummies, leather and plant materials.

To significantly mitigate the damage, the HVAC system will maintain proper temperature and RH which will discourage pest activity, while the double-door entrance system, closing windows and the airtightness of the showcases will enormously improve the sealing.

3.4 Air quality (dust and pollutants)

The location of the EM with large quantities of dust, and varied pollutants due to the surrounding high traffic contributed to the deterioration of its collections, including that of Tutankhamun. The unsealed building and the lack of ventilation made the situation worse and affected the whole collection.

The sealed GEM building envelops will ensure the reduction or elimination of dust and pollutants. The HVAC system also comprises good quality filters for all vents, to cut pollutants out of air intake cycles. All materials and fabrication methods for all furniture including panels, platforms, artefact cases, etc. are chemically stable, and were approved by the GEM-CC. Moreover, airtight showcases will more effectively block external airborne pollutants. The collection will be installed in cases at least one month after completing the paint, adhesive and sealant works, to protect it from harmful volatile materials.

4. Mitigating physical damage in the Tutankhamun galleries

It is no exaggeration to say that severe damage could occur to collections in display because of physical factors. As a result of the collection survey, it was clear that physical damage has occurred due to improper mounting materials and techniques, and unsuitable case design. One bad example is the beard in the golden mask of Tutankhamun which was detached during attempts to change the case light bulb. Physical damage may also occur during object handling for conservation, replacement on display, etc. as a result of the improper placement of objects or overcrowding in the showcases. Consequently, it was agreed that the layout of the showcases should allow easy and simple access to artefacts and graphic elements, which will inevitably require maintenance or replacement. Additionally, most of the artefacts will be mounted without using hanging or suspension. The configuration of mounts was assessed by conservators, individually or by type of artefact.

As a result, objects will be presented inside the cases using either of three categories of mounting; the lay/put method, standard mounts and special mounts. Lay/put involves installing objects on the showcase bottom, plinth or shelf without any additional mounts, and is suitable for chairs and stools. The additional standard mounts, predefined in form and surface, but adapted to the particular exhibit, will conveniently be used with boat models, shabtis, jewellery, plates and arrows. In cases where standard mounts do not fit the object's shape or surface; for example, collars, earrings and textiles, custom-made mounts will be used. The design and fabrication of this category of mounts will be a direct collaboration between exhibit designers, mount makers and conservators. In each case, contact between objects and mounts will be avoided.

5. Conclusion

The GEM functions primarily to preserve its collection, which has long been suffering from improper display and/or storage conditions. It was quite a challenge designing the galleries which will display the King Tutankhamun collection in time for the museum's soft opening. This addressed the great damage detected through a survey of the collection, and the desire to, for the first time, display the whole collection in a nearly optimal display environment. Therefore, conservation was involved early and throughout the process, to ensure preservation through responsible planning, design and production. The conservation professionals in the GEM firstly embarked on assessing risks to the collection to prioritise the preventive conservation needs in the gallery within the scope of sustainability and energy consumption and considering the special climate requirements for certain objects.

As a starting point, general preventive conservation guidelines explaining the general criteria for designing the galleries spaces and cases, environmental conditions, mounts and materials were developed and

presented to the designers. Furthermore, a list detailing the materials, condition and optimal display environment for each artefact was generated. The collaboration between all parties; conservators, curators, engineers and exhibit designers, throughout the process and until reaching the final design, resolved a number of issues. For example, environmental control sparked very much debate among parties. Some of the lively discussions were about how to display a set of objects in one showcase to serve a curatorial concept, when one of those objects had completely different preservation requirements from the others. Good evaluation of condition presented by conservators made the voice of conservation heard. The discussions led to a case-in-case design in which the degraded object will be in a completely controlled microenvironment isolated from the large case comprising the rest of the objects. Such planning will accomplish the key function of the museum, that of 'preserving the collection', in the best possible way.

Preventive conservation practice in the galleries involves displaying the collection in airtight showcases which mainly utilise passive RH buffering for climate control. The airtightness of the showcases mitigates pests and air quality issues at case level, and further-more reduces energy consumption at the building level and promotes sustainability at case level. The building envelope is generally well sealed, so environmental fluctuations, as well as pest ingress and air pollution, are mitigated. Daylight is also eliminated and specified types of LEDs are used in the gallery spaces and showcases.

References

- Bickersteth, J. 2014. "Environmental Conditions for Safeguarding Collections: What Should our Set Points Be?" *Studies in Conservation* 59: 218–224.
- Bratasz, Ł. 2013. "Allowable Microclimatic Variations in Museums and Historic Buildings: Reviewing the Guidelines." In *Climate for Collections: Standards and Uncertainties*, edited by J. Ashley-Smith, A. Burmester, and M. Eibl, 11–19. London: Archetype.
- Elmarazky, A., O. Aboelkheir, H. Kamal, E. Abdallah, and A. Rashed. 2017. "Impact of Previous Chemical Treatment and Environmental Storage Conditions on Miniature Hoes from Tutankhamun's Tomb." In *ICOM-CC 18th Triennial Meeting Copenhagen Preprints*, edited by J. Bridgland. Paris: ICOM-CC. <http://icom-cc-publications-online.org/PublicationList.aspx?search=&wg=0&vy=Copenhagen+2017&t=0&page=1..>
- Lake, C. 2011. "Exhibit Construction: Conservation, Preservation, Materials, and Design: Focus on the Pro Football Hall of Fame Canton, Ohio." unpublished dissertation, Master of Arts Administration, Theatre Arts-Administration, University of Akron and Ohio.
- Muething, G., R. Waller, and F. Graham. 2005. "Risk Assessment of Collections in Exhibitions at the Canadian Museum of Nature." *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation* 44 (3): 233–243.
- Pedersoli, J. L., C. Antomarchi, and S. Michalski. 2016. *A Guide to Risk Management of Cultural Heritage*, edited by Z. Aslan, and A. Sabik. Rome: ICCROM & Canadian Conservation Institute.
- Raphael, T., and M. Burke. 2000. "A Set of Conservation Guidelines for Exhibitions." Objects Specialty Group Postprints, *American Institute for Conservation of Historic & Artistic Works* 7: 5–20.
- Shiner, J. 2007. "Trends in Microclimate Control of Museum Display Cases." In *Museum Microclimates*, edited by T. Padfield, and K. Borchersen, 267–275. Copenhagen: National Museum of Denmark.
- Smith, S. 2010. *Victoria and Albert Museum: Guidelines for the Environmental Control for Objects on Display in Future Plan*. London: Victoria and Albert Museum.
- Staniforth, S. 2014. "Environmental Conditions for the Safeguarding of Collections: Future Trends." *Studies in Conservation* 59: 213–217.